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**THE HISTORY AND CONTEMPORARY DEVELOPMENT OF
TRADITIONAL HANDICRAFTS IN UZBEKISTAN**

Annotation. This thesis provides detailed information about handicrafts, its brief definition and the history of the development of handicrafts in Uzbekistan. Historically, it is known that craft was created by the production activity of man, during the development of society, it was gradually separated from agriculture and animal husbandry, it was improved in connection with the development of technology within the framework of different socio-historical periods, and it was divided into different specializations. After independence, the government paid special attention to the development of national crafts in our country.

Key word: Handicrafts, labor weapons, neolithic period, Khorezm Oasis, crafts, agricultural crafts, "master".

Handicrafts — national-a type of industry based on the production of traditional fine goods, individual and manual labor using ordinary labor weapons; the general name of the professions in which such products are prepared. Large-scale industrial production was widespread until its inception, with some industries still retained after. It still occupies an important place in the national economy of less developed countries. The handicrafts became stratified as it was drawn more broadly and deeper into commodity-money relations.

Handicrafts arose with human productive activities, gradually separated from agriculture and livestock throughout the development of society, began to improve in connection with the development of technology within the framework of various socio-historical periods, were divided into various specialties, for example, pottery, carpentry, blacksmithing, miscarriages, etc. Depending on what natural resources are available, such as cotton and sawdust on the ground, quality raw materials on the ground, pottery, wool and leather on the ground, textiles and tanning, accordingly, agriculture, woodworking on the forest floor, metalworking on the ore-rich lands, and ironmaking, shipbuilding on the seas and rivers, etc.

On the territory of Uzbekistan, in the neolithic period, the production and weaving of pottery, which was considered the first important branch of crafts, arose (Kaltaminor culture in the Khorezm Oasis, Sopollitepa in Surkhandarya, etc.). From the 2nd century BC, The Great Silk Road became important in the trade in handicrafts. In the Middle Ages, products made in Eastern countries (steel in the Arab Caliphate, silk in Central Asia and India, porcelain, paper) were appreciated in European markets. In India, elegant fabric from cotton, in China,

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silk fabric weaving looms appeared, in China and Central Asia, glass making technology began to improve.

In the early 1st millennium BC, the Iron Age begins as a result of the appropriation of making various weapons and tools from iron.¹

In the 9th and 10th centuries, large craft centers appeared in Middle Asia. Silk cloth, carpet (Urganch, Shosh), silk (Marv), copper and iron weapons, knife making (Fergana), silk fabrics, glass products making (Bukhara) were in full swing. In the 13th century, the Mongol invasion hit the development of crafts. The emergence of the Timurid state had a very positive effect on the development of crafts.

All types of crafts in Central Asia were preserved until the 20s of the 20th century. Craftsmanship played a large role in the production of cities such as Bukhara, Samarkand, Kokand, Khiva, Tashkent (in the 60s of the 19th century, 27 types of crafts developed in Khiva, in the markets of the city there were 556 shops of artisans, in the 80s in the city there were 2528 agricultural crafts).

At the time of the first population census in 1897, the majority of the population in large cities were considered artisans. For example, 64% of Namangan's population, 52% of Kokand, 54% of Chust, 50% of Margilon, were considered independent professional.²

In the 20s of the 20th century, with the decision of the authorities of the showrooms, the main part of the craftsmen was attracted at first to artels, and later, to factories, enterprises of art objects. Raw materials, materials, tools were supplied to them by the state, created products were sold through shops and a state's cooperative. Talented craftsmen were accepted into creative organizations, the art of practical decoration was developed (for example, in the 1930s, an educational production combine was established in Tashkent, young craftsmen were educated in it, in 1968 a craftsmen school workshop was founded in Bukhara, and in 1978 a woodcarving school workshop was founded in Kokand).

After Uzbekistan gained independence, a new era began in the development of crafts, folk crafts were revived in the basic of market rules. As a result, of the privatization of local industrial enterprises in Uzbekistan, among the first, small state-owned enterprises were transformed into private enterprises of trade-mandes, new handicraft enterprises were opened. Crafts began to work not only on the domestic market, but also on exports. The organizational form of handicrafts also changed: a small family enterprise began to develop in the form of individual labor activity. On October 24-25, 1995, the 1st Republican Fair of people's Masters and artisans of Uzbekistan was held in Tashkent in practical cooperation with the UN Permanent Mission to Uzbekistan. In 1997, the Creative Production Association "master" of masters of folk Applied Arts and crafts of the Republic was founded. The decree of the first president of the Republic of March 31, 1997 "On measures to support the further development of folk art crafts and

¹ Usmonov K., Sodikov M., Burkhonova S. History of Uzbekistan. Textbook. – T., 2005. -24-p.

² Iso Jabborov. Ethnography of the Uzbek people. T.:1993 y. P.63

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applied art by the state way"and other measures were instrumental in the revival and further development of crafts in Uzbekistan, the revival of some of its forgotten types. Craftsmen first entered the Chamber of commodity producers of Uzbekistan, and then the Chamber of Commerce and industry. They were merged into a special organization — the Republican Association "Craftsman". Craft subjects participate in the annual "initiative" Republican competition of entrepreneurs, artisans and farms in Uzbekistan. During the period 1996-2005, 10 craftsmen were recognized as the winner of the "initiative" competition for their achievements in folk crafts.

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